

Effective Ways of Organizing Work on Guiding Blind Students to Professions

Khaitgul Muzaffarova ¹, Sajida Kushmurodova ²

¹ Jizzakh State Pedagogical University Department of special pedagogy Doctor of philosophy in pedagogical sciences (PhD)

² Special pedagogy, defectology (speechology) II stage master's degree

Abstract:

In the article, the opinions and comments about the tasks of preparing visually impaired students for the conscious choice of socially necessary professions are expressed.

Keywords: Blind student, career guidance, special skills, science, test, book, interest, inclination, ability, opportunity.

The problem of choosing a profession is of national importance. Vocational guidance implies a number of psychological-pedagogical, medical and organizational measures. It supports the conscious approach of the graduates to the choice of profession and its compliance with the requirements of the society, the response to the requirements of the national economy in terms of social economy, and the individual development of each student. The readiness of students to choose a profession depends on several factors, including knowledge of the most common language of work, knowledge of the physical and mental requirements of a person, one or another profession to learn about the ways of occupation, to choose a profession with a correct assessment of personal characteristics.

Vocational guidance includes vocational information, vocational diagnosis, vocational selection and vocational adoption in accordance with the tasks of vocational selection. Each component has its own purpose and methods. The first step in career guidance is career information. Providing information about the profession implies that blind children have knowledge about the profession, about the labor activity of each of them, about the requirements that the profession imposes on a person, where it is possible to acquire this profession. Information about the profession is given in various forms, including during the learning process of science teachers, in conversations with

students in labor education classes, during excursions, when showing movies, in meetings when training conferences are organized.

According to the results of the inspections carried out in the next decade, visually impaired students also have information about the types of professions and the requirements for work in them. As a result, there is uniformity in students' choice of profession, professional interests are not constant. In addition, blind children choose a profession that does not take into account their speech. Therefore, the first task is to provide an understanding of professions, mainly deaf-friendly professions. Introducing deaf people to professions is connected with the demand for deaf people in this city and village.

The second organizational element of introduction to the profession is counseling. Its purpose is to determine whether the child's psychophysical capabilities match the profession chosen by the child. This part of the work has several difficulties. It's not about determining the students' abilities and jobs, but about the individual characteristics of each student. Vocational counseling aims to match the type of profession chosen by the child with the characteristics of mental development with the requirements placed on him.

The third task is to identify possible opportunities for further development of a person. The role of the pedagogue in the organization of professional guidance is great, and he should study the student's personality in a comprehensive way using various methods. The school doctor also provided a lot of help, his task is to study the development of psychophysical mechanisms in depth, to strengthen the physical development of a blind child.

In the organization of professional counseling, legal counseling and departments processing questions on labor law, as well as leaders in production and parental referrals play an important role.

In the deep and comprehensive study of a blind student, a professional diagnosis that determines his or her readiness for one or another profession is integrated. It determines biological, mental, social readiness. A component of career guidance is a professional competition conducted by specialists of educational institutions and members of the organization.

The final stage of vocational guidance is the adaptation of young workers to the workplace. Production teams should help young workers overcome the challenge. Teacher educators should monitor the employment and adaptation of graduates. While a general educational institution - a boarding school - is assigned a major task in the implementation of vocational guidance, important tasks are also assigned to other communities (labor communities, deaf communities).

Parents are actively involved in determining their children's career and life plans. However, the tests showed that the advice of parents does not match with the opinion of the pedagogue and the possibilities and interests of the students. Therefore, parents of blind children have an understanding of their interests, capabilities, aspirations, and inclinations.

Introducing parents to these tasks by the pedagogue helps to differentiate the parent community, students are given a description of the development of uniform requirements and the choice of future professions. Our future depends on the young people we are raising today. This law also depends on the activity of the family in terms of education. The complexity of family education is that each family is a unique universe. It also shows its own characteristics in educational work.

It is possible to ensure the well-being of the growing young generation only if family education is closely connected with social education. Achievements in family education depend on providing parents with pedagogical knowledge, sharing experiences on family education, and actively involving parents in educational activities.

It is up to every parent to have a deep understanding of their duties and responsibilities in raising their children. In addition, a normal family environment, the authority of parents, a correct daily routine, and timely involvement of the child in books, study, and work are also a guarantee of success.

It can be seen that the problem of raising a smart, insightful, deep-thinking child - in a word, a mature child - has been urgent since ancient times, today, tomorrow, and in the future. People love, honor and respect such virtuous people.

The family has 2 duties before society:

- natural biological function;
- Social function.

It is the natural biological task of a person to give birth to a child, as it is characteristic of all living beings. The second main task that is unique to humans is the social task of raising the children who come into this world to be people who serve the society and the country. It can be seen that family upbringing is not the private work of parents, but also the duty of the state to the society, because if a child grows up, not only the parents, but also the whole country, neighborhood and the state will benefit from him.

Our blessed sources are "Qur'an", "Hadiths", Qabusnama, "Shahnama", "Temurnoma", "Boburnoma", "Guliston", "Bo'ston", "Temur Tuzuklari", which are the spiritual heritage of our ancestors. Anyone who has read such masterpieces as "Kutadgu Bilig" and "Maqbul ul Qulub" is convinced that education is an important factor in human formation.

Regarding the complexity of education, Amir Temur said, "I am convinced that raising a child requires a deeper observation and even deeper wisdom than managing a state."

"Education is a matter of life, death, salvation, destruction, happiness or disaster for us," he said. He emphasizes that education should be shaped by the family, and for this, parents themselves should be educated. Teach the child to work from a young age. A person does not suddenly become a hard worker. First of all, let your children know whether they have done the work you ordered them to do, even if it is half-baked or incomplete, and encourage them in appropriate ways. Praise that you will take my work away from me.

Teach your children to work independently and think independently as much as possible. For example, if he asks you for help in a subject, don't work it out for your child, just explain it. After solving the problem, cheer him up by saying: "You can easily solve it yourself." That's how your child will gain self-confidence.

Teach your children about household chores. Do what you can do according to your age.

In the conditions of Uzbekistan, the content of family education has its own aspects, which we cannot ignore. Economic conditions, climate, natural features of our country, wide development of cotton cultivation, horticulture significantly affects the economic and social development of the population of our Republic, each family, changes in family conditions, and children's education.

Our republic has its own characteristics in terms of its democratic, ethnic national conditions. For example: rapid increase in population density, large number of children, respect for elders, father's position, hospitality, pity for women, uniqueness of raising boys and girls, training for work, preparation for family life. It is impossible to achieve success in raising children to become well-rounded people without connecting the school with the family. Therefore, the school should expand the work related to education among parents. Parents' feedback during teacher-teacher conferences is especially valuable for parents, as they learn more about their children. Therefore, every parent

who has forgotten the essence of child education strives to strengthen the cooperation between the family and the school.

Until the child enters school and graduates, parents should establish close contact with the school, always be aware of their child's learning and behavior, consult with the teacher and head of the class on educational issues. He should let the child know what he is doing. The teacher, in turn, needs to convey information about the child's studies, manners, behavior, and behavior at school to the parents, and solve problems together when necessary. Only then will it be possible to make a uniform demand to the student. Parents whose children go to school become members of this team. Therefore, parents must actively participate in the social life of the school. It is necessary to establish strong cooperation between the teacher and the student's family. It is very important for parents to cooperate with neighborhood activists and labor veterans in the field of education. These activities make a significant contribution to family education. Family, school and community (neighborhood) cooperation is required to raise a perfect child.

In conclusion, it can be said that in the conditions of current economic and social changes, the attention to the issues of family education is increasing and becoming a topical issue.

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